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CLIMATE NEUTRAL BUILDING DESIGN ATELIER FOR ARCHITECTURE STUDENTS

Align architectural education with the paramount energy
and climate goals of the green transition in Europe

Af

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Disclaimer

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CONTENT

04	Introduction
04	Context of the Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier
04	Goals and objectives of the Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier
05	Content of the Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier
07	Implementation of the Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier
07	Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier at University of Zagreb
08	Pjenica 2.0.
14	Blok Badel
20	design hub
28	Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier at University Of Architecture And Urbanism ‘Ion Mincu’ Bucharest
29	Dynamic Renewable Sustainable Rehabilitation
36	University Urban Slab
44	Spatial Continuity through Sustainability
52	Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier at New Bulgarian University
53	Mramor Lake Park Residential Complex
59	Mramor Mixed type Residential Complex
64	Residential Eco-Community in Mramor
69	Promotion and Dissemination of the Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier
69	Final International Event of the Incept Project
73	Atelier certificate of completion
74	Conclusions

Introduction

Context of the Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier

The educational curriculum proposed by INCEPT project within the Master of Architecture programmes of partner universities is composed of:

- 1) Lecture course on sustainable architecture for architecture students,
- 2) Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier for architecture students,
- 3) Online course on sustainable architecture for the wider professional community.

The implementation of Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier concept is aligned with the specific objective SO2: to train architecture students on how to design more energy-efficient, less carbon-intensive and more sustainable buildings in the wider multi-faceted urban context allowing room for creativity and aesthetic decisions. In pursuit of this specific objective, the project foresees as an intellectual output to create Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier for architecture students to test energy efficient design concepts, practical ideas and tools as part of their training in a "living lab" ecosystem. Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier will contribute to alignment of architectural education with the paramount energy and climate goals of the green transition in Europe.

A new approach to education focuses on carbon neutrality, circularity, and sustainability, aligning with the UN's sustainable development goals. This approach is also embedded within the New European Bauhaus platform, which combines sustainability, inclusion, and aesthetics.

The development of the methodology, stages and content of the design training atelier is one of the three main Intellectual Outputs of INCEPT Project: IO3 Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier for architecture students.

Objective of the Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier

The objective of this initiative is to educate architecture students on energy efficiency principles and sustainable design practices across the entire building lifecycle.

Goals of the Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier

- Promote circularity, reuse, and lifecycle considerations in architectural education.
- Utilize elective courses to address various environments and case studies.
- Understand the impact of architecture on climate change and urban sustainability.
- Examine themes and approaches treating various scales.
- Address the reuse of existing built stock and develop innovative climate-neutral building solutions.
- Engage various departments and numerous guest experts.

Content of the Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier

The implementation of the Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier at partner universities.

Topic

Reuse and circularity in architectural education, focusing on brownfields or heritage sites.

Approach

- Partner institutions select brownfield or heritage sites within their environments.
- Joint research on potential programs for the site: historical significance, reprogramming potential, urban impact.
- Develop interventions related to redesign, reprogramming, urban design, and energy performance.
- Align with the EU Urban Agenda on circular economy and resource use.
- Design multifunctional spaces for cultural, educational, and public use.
- Place emphasis on public access, cultural spaces, green infrastructure, and energy performance improvements.

Activities

- Initial one-week intensive workshop with site visits and research.
- Two weeks of joint research to define specific interests.
- Group divisions based on interests, with mentor guidance.
- Lectures, intermediate presentations, project development, and final public presentations.

Methodology and Tutors

The design studio tackles a single design problem from various angles, involving teachers and practitioners. It covers low-tech or vernacular climate design, zero-energy principles, sustainable urban planning, and sociological impacts of healthy cities.

Atelier involved teachers from various departments/studios (architecture, urban planning, and building technology). External guest lecturers included municipal office representatives, practicing architects, urban planners, conservationists, heritage experts, brownfield redesign experts, and other faculty members from various departments.

Duration

one semester

ECTS Distribution

The Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier is an elective studio awarding 5 ECTS.

The studio structure can be adapted to meet other curricular frameworks.

Content of the Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier

Outcomes

Scales of ReUse: Thematic Student Distribution

1. Re-design, Addition Design, and Reprogramming (STUDIO A – architecture)

- Focus on the adaptive reuse of existing buildings.
- Develop new functions and additions that complement the historical structure.
- Enhance energy efficiency and sustainability through innovative design solutions.

2. Urban Design of Area, Future Development, Green Infrastructure (STUDIO U - urban planning)

- Create a cohesive urban plan that integrates the site with its surrounding context.
- Emphasize green infrastructure and pedestrian connectivity.
- Propose future developments that support social and public content, improving the quality of life for residents and develop neighborhoods.

3. Improving Energy Performance of Structures, Developing Additions Based on Zero-Energy Principles – Detailing for Zero-Emission Reconstruction (STUDIO T - structures and building technology)

- Focus on technical solutions for achieving zero-energy standards.
- Detail the reconstruction of existing buildings to enhance their energy performance.
- Incorporate sustainable materials and construction methods.

Student groups are distributed so that a minimum of 3 participants cover each thematic focus – architecture, urban planning and building technology.

Presentation Format and Project Delivery

The drawings elaborated within the project were delivered in digital format, respecting the requirements described below. This type of approach was intended to encourage students to participate in architectural competitions, to familiarize them with the drafting and teaching rigour of the projects, and at the same time have the purpose of drafting a catalogue of projects. A selection of drawings and renderings was presented in printed format for the purposes of the final exhibition.

- Summary poster, written in English, printed in 70 x 100 cm format (vertically paginated), for each of the 3 scales - U, A, T.
- A3 (horizontal) booklet in .pdf format, aligned with a provided digital template unified for the group/semester. This booklet included all the conducted analyses, texts, drawings and renderings made by the groups' participants.

The Atelier results presented in this brochure comprise selected student projects of all three partner universities:

- University of Zagreb,
- University of Architecture and Urbanism 'Ion Mincu' Bucharest,
- New Bulgarian University.

The student projects are presented chronologically, as the Atelier was not held at the partner universities at the same time. Each of the partner universities will be presented by three student projects.

Implementation of the Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier

UNIVERSITY OF ZAGREB

Introduction

The specific focus of the test Atelier in academic year 2023/2024 were "Scales of Re-use," utilizing the Blok Badel site as a key case study. A selected site was Blok Badel Distillery, a neglected and unfinished area of Zagreb surrounded by Vlaška Street, Kvaternik Square, Martić Street and Derenčinova street and its wider contact zone. Student proposals had to be aligned with the results of the Blok Badel competition (which was conducted by the City of Zagreb in 2012), numerous studies and the current Urban development plan. The Blok Badel site (including Pjenica heritage building) represents an extremely significant spatial resource that can play a significant role in forming the identity and pulse of this part of the city.

Timeline

At the University of Zagreb (Faculty of Architecture) the Atelier took place in the winter semester of academic year 2023/2024, in the period from October 2023 to January 2024. Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier was conducted for four hours each week. Twenty-eight students attended the atelier. Students were divided into five groups, each consisting of 5 or 6 students.

Site challenges

- Urban Conflicts: The industrial development led to conflicts in land use atypical for the Zagreb Lower Town block structure.
- Unfinished Development: The Blok Badel area remains the only block in the Lower Town district of Zagreb that is unfinished and lacks a clear urban structure and purpose.
- Plans for Future Development: Integrate the new city plan for the development of mixed-use buildings at the area's perimeter and interpolate the reuse of protected buildings and public spaces taking these developments into account.

Mentors

Ana Mrđa, PhD Arch, Associate Professor
 Mia Roth-Čerina, PhD Arch, Professor
 Zoran Veršić, PhD Arch, Professor
 Marin Binički, Arch, Senior Lect.
 Stanka Ostojić, Arch, Senior Lect.

Guest Lecturers

UPI-2M studio
 Snježana Turalija, DGNB Consultant
 Nataša Aralica, Urban Planner
 Iva Rechner Dika, Assistant Professor at School of Landscape Architecture, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Zagreb

Pjenica 2.0.

Students

Katja Marasović
 Lara Marasović
 Katarina Miloš Rimac
 Mirjana Meštrović
 Darija Obradović
 Dorotea Orišković

The concept of the newly designed state was based on an analysis of the existing scope and resulted in the renovation of the old Pjenica Building and the construction of its “twin” adjacent to it. The analysis highlighted key elements, such as the elementary school near the Kvatrić market, but also revealed a lack of important cultural functions. These factors led to the idea of dedicating both the old and new Pjenica to cultural and artistic uses. Furthermore, the nearby elementary school influenced the design of the multifunctional hall in the new Pjenica. The original Pjenica was conceived as a space for exhibitions, education, and workshops that support the development of local artists. Its spatial composition consists of a ground-floor exhibition area with accompanying functions (education and workshops) located in a gallery on the upper floors. The new Pjenica is connected to the old one through a multifunctional hall, designed for courses, events, and sports activities, directly inspired by the elementary school.

The hall is located on the upper floor, while the ground floor serves as a market area with the option of opening towards the plot itself. This creates a strong connection with the iconic Kvatrić market and defines a zone that supports the further development of local agriculture. Since both the old and new Pjenica are located within a city block, the design of the plot follows accordingly. It is organized in a regular grid with multifunctional pavilions, a mix of low and tall greenery, and paved surfaces. This diverse arrangement extends the theme of Pjenica into the outdoor space, offering engaging activities for the residents of the block. The green areas also accommodate playgrounds, dog parks, and lounge zones in nature. The overall aim of the project is to enrich the cultural life of this part of the city through both spatial design and programmatic content. By offering flexible spaces and functions, the concept attracts a broad spectrum of users, raises the quality of life in the neighborhood, and creates opportunities for community development.

results

Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier

results

Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier

0 2 4 10m

section a-a: old vs. new pjenica

section a-a: old vs. new penica
0 1 2 5m

Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier results

Blok Badel

Students

Goran Antunović
Eric Ivić
Mateo Liović
Boris Juraj Lovrinčević
Mijo Mandurić

The urban design of the Badel block responds to the immediate and wider urban context in terms of content, disposition, and form. Building on the role of the “Pjenica” building—preserved as a protected cultural heritage landmark and repurposed into a sports facility—the theme of sports, a largely absent function in the dense urban fabric, is extended into the ground floor of the Badel block. The block interior is structured into two elongated zones divided by an east–west pedestrian path, which expands into a square in front of the “Pjenica” building. Sports playgrounds are positioned to the east and west, spanning the width of the block and defining its northern zone. The southern zone is designed as a park interwoven with small-scale urban elements, including children’s playgrounds and outdoor fitness areas. These functions are connected by circulation routes defined both by existing and planned entrances, as well as by the division of the block into a north–south belt. According to the urban plan, the block perimeter is framed by buildings of P+4, and P+5. The main entrances are located along Martičeva Street and Pavla Šubića Street, where the plan does not envisage continuous frontage, except for terrace extensions of ground-floor uses. Additional passages through the block are provided from Derenčinova and Vlaška Streets to ensure permeability in all directions. Pavla Šubića Street is closed to vehicular traffic and transformed into a pedestrian zone, linking three important public spaces—Kvatrić Square, Kvatrić Market, and Blok Badel.

The architectural concept emphasizes the complete preservation of the existing building footprint and the maximum retention of spatial, structural, and dispositional relationships. Given the lack of sports facilities in the immediate and wider surroundings of this part of Zagreb, the “Pjenica” building is adapted in program to serve as a sports facility. The floor plan is organized into three zones: two elongated service wings forming an L-shape along the outer edges, which enclose the main hall. This principle has been maintained in the new design: the service areas accommodate functions such as changing rooms, toilets, lobbies, and storage, while the central halls are dedicated to competition and training spaces. Vertical circulation is relocated to the junction of the two service wings to improve functionality and spatial flow. The distribution of competition areas is guided by the existing floor heights: the main hall with a basketball court and spectator seating occupies the second floor; a gym is placed on the first floor; and the ground-floor multifunctional hall is designed for sports and other events. The existing annex is glazed and expanded to include an additional store, while a mezzanine level with a wellness zone is added above the ground-floor service area.

results

Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier

10
5
2
1
0

results

Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier

section / details

BLOK BADEL

students

Eric Ivić
Mateo Liović
Boris Juraj Lovrinčević
Goran Antunović
Mijo Mandurić

mentors

Ana Mrda, PhD Arch, Associate Professor
Mia Roth-Čerina, PhD Arch, Professor
Zoran Veršić, PhD Arch, Professor
Marin Binički, Arch, Senior Lect.
Stanka Ostojić, Arch, Senior Lect.

The Badel block's urban design builds on its surroundings, preserving the central heritage-listed Pjenica building, now repurposed as a sports facility to address the lack of such spaces in central Zagreb. Sports courts extend east and west of the building, forming the block's northern zone, while a park with playgrounds and outdoor fitness areas occupies the southern zone. Pathways follow existing and planned block entrances, ensuring full accessibility.

Per the urban plan, the block's edges are lined with mostly P+4 and P+5 buildings. Main entrances are on Martičeva and Pavla Šubića Streets, with additional pedestrian connections through Dencenčova and Vlaška. Pavla Šubića is converted into a car-free zone, linking Kvatrić Square, Market, and the Badel block.

The Pjenica building retains its original structure, repurposed into a sports center with service zones and three main activity areas: a ground-floor multifunctional hall, a first-floor gym, and a top-floor basketball court with an auditorium. A wellness mezzanine and glazed extension with added storage are also included.

design hub

Students

Fran Klarić
 Vanesa Korlević
 Stjepan Sorić
 Nikola Toplek
 Jakov Vranković

As part of the revitalization of the Badel block, several structures from the former factory complex are preserved, including the Pjenica building and two facades of the peripheral buildings. The undeveloped parts of the block are transformed into public pedestrian areas, while the Pjenica building is repurposed as a design hub—an incubator for designers within the Zagreb design district. The design intervention relies on subtle, reflective volumes placed both inside the Pjenica building and across the surrounding public space. These unobtrusive insertions create fragmented enclosed areas that accommodate shops and service spaces within the retained building. In the surrounding outdoor areas, the dematerialized reflective structures function as exits from underground garages, bicycle storage, retail for designers and artisans, or cafés. Together with landscaped green hills, they fragment the block, form resting and play areas, provide settings for larger events, and define pedestrian movement corridors between the block's entrances. The green elements are conceived either as raised mounds above underground garages or as depressions on the Pjenica plot itself. These allow for tree planting above the garages and serve as rainwater retention basins. At the western edge of the block, an exhibition square is created, directly connected to the gallery space within the design hub. From the south, the building is approached via a new access square, while a larger green depression to the east is shaped as a flexible space serving as an auditorium, concert hall, and rainwater retention basin. At the far eastern end of the block, a children's playground is located next to the planned kindergarten. Inside the Pjenica building, the design hub accommodates its new program. The ground floor contains exhibition and lecture spaces that can be extended outdoors into the western square. Support functions such as toilets, an information desk, and storage areas are designed as reflective volumes that emphasize their later insertion within the historic shell. Their dematerialized appearance introduces lightness and dynamism to the interior while maintaining a minimal and almost temporary prefabricated character.

The upper floor offers workspaces for individual and group activities, alongside classrooms and meeting rooms contained in enclosed volumes. The top floor, conceived as a double-height space, is divided into two large workshops equipped for model making and fabrication. Between them, inserted volumes house storage and technical equipment. Above these service areas, a winter garden with a glazed roof provides additional daylight to the workshops. Technical installations, including the HVAC unit and heat pump, are in two attic rooms at the southern end of the building. To the southwest, the retained suspended canopy serves as a covered entrance, complemented by a café below it with an outdoor terrace. The renovation strategy respects the existing steel frame with prestressed concrete slab reinforcement and non-load-bearing brick infill. For seismic strengthening, the FRCM system is applied externally to the masonry elements. The envelope is upgraded with 2 cm of aerogel insulation, while interior walls expose the original brick without added finishes. New inserted volumes are constructed of laminated beech, with interiors clad in beech plywood, carpet, or tiles depending on use. Exteriors are finished in highly polished stainless steel for durability and reflectivity, with beech plywood surfaces used only indoors. Visible ventilation ducts emphasize the industrial character of the space. Sustainability was a guiding principle of the renovation. Measures include retaining the existing structure, applying highly insulating materials, and reusing on-site resources such as humus from earthworks, which is used to shape the green mounds. Anti-traumatic playground surfaces are made of recycled rubber. Beyond material strategies, the very program of the design hub—with its workshops dedicated to repair and reuse—supports a circular economy, reinforcing the building's new identity as a sustainable cultural and creative incubator for the Zagreb design district.

results
Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier

DESIGN HUB

students
 Fran Klarić
 Vanesa Korlević
 Sijepan Sorić
 Nikola Topček
 Jakov Vranković

mentors
 Ana Mrđa, PhD Arch, Associate Professor
 Mia Roth-Ćerina, PhD Arch, Professor
 Zoran Veršić, PhD Arch, Professor
 Marin Binički, Arch, Senior Lect.
 Stanka Ostojić, Arch, Senior Lect.

As part of the Badel block revitalization, the historic Pjenica building and two façade fragments are preserved. The unused area becomes a public pedestrian zone, and Pjenica is transformed into a design hub and incubator for the Zagreb design district. Reflective, minimal volumes are added to shape functional spaces like shops, bike storage, and cafés, while green mounds and depressions enable rest areas, events, and water retention. The design hub includes exhibition and lecture spaces on the ground floor, workspaces and meeting rooms above, and workshops with natural light and a winter garden on the top floor. A café with a covered terrace sits under the existing canopy. The building is seismically reinforced, thermally insulated with aerogel, and uses sustainable materials like recycled rubber and visible brick. The renovation emphasizes circular economy and reuse, combining modern design with heritage conservation.

Implementation of the Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier

"ION MINCU" UNIVERSITY OF ARCHITECTURE AND URBANISM, BUCHAREST (UAUIM)

Introduction

The INCEPT Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier at UAUIM is designed as a significant step in emphasizing the essential balance between creativity and sustainability, driven by the growing need to envision and realize climate-neutral built environments, inspiring a new era in architectural education.

The "Living Lab" provided students with hands-on learning experience where they could explore the intricate relationship between sustainability, technology, and design.

The proposed framework theme referred to the design of an intervention on the buildings of the "Ion Mincu" University of Architecture and Urban Planning, including the adjacent urban spaces, through possible sustainable urban regeneration measures.

Timeline

Over a 12-week period between March and May 2024, during the second semester of the 2023–2024 academic year, the 'Living Lab' Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier was conducted at the 'Ion Mincu' University of Architecture and Urban Planning in Bucharest, engaging fifth-year architecture students. This innovative design atelier was conducted for four hours each week. 117 students attended the atelier. Students were divided into 13 groups, each consisting of 8-9 students, divided on 3 scales of approaching the project: Urban, Architectural and Technical (U, A, T).

Site challenges

The core theme focuses on designing an intervention for the building complex of the "Ion Mincu" University of Architecture and Urbanism and its adjacent urban spaces, aiming for sustainable urban regeneration. This involves a multi-criteria analysis of the urban block defined by the UAUIM buildings and its relationship with the surrounding spaces/streets, proposals for urban regeneration that integrate UAUIM as a cultural landmark and a nucleus for sustainable development, improving the quality of urban spaces through sustainable design principles in relation to the pillars of sustainable development (environmental, social, economic, cultural), architectural interventions on existing buildings (functional reconfigurations, extensions, facades, energy performance), and detailed technical proposals for increasing energy efficiency and implementing sustainability principles, all carried out in stages through defining the theme, documentation, establishing analysis criteria, intervention principles and strategies, sustainability concepts and preparing the corresponding drawings.

Mentors

Daniel Armenciu, PhD Arch. Senior Lect.
 Angelica Stan, PhD Arch, Professor
 Mihaela Hărmănescu, PhD Arch, Assoc. Professor
 Sorin Manea, PhD Arch. Lect.
 Zina Macri, PhD Arch, Assoc. Professor
 Oana Mihăescu, PhD Arch. Senior Lect.
 Andreea Prelipcean, PhD Arch. Senior Lect.
 Oana Avram, PhD Arch. Senior Lect.

Guest Lecturers

Rodica Crișan, PhD Arch. Professor
 Adrian Vidrașcu, PhD Arch. Senior Lect.

Dynamic Renewable Sustainable Rehabilitation

Students

Ana Popescu
Cristiana Roman
David Mircea
Filip Radu Tudor
Ioana Bors
Irina Nedelcu
Larissa Danci
Madalina-Roxana Costea
Sabrina Tudor

The main objective of the project is centered around the "UAUIM Courtyard," creating a vibrant multifunctional space dedicated to students, but also opened and actively communicating to the public space around the building. The solution address several existing issues noticed at urban, architectural and technical detailing scale, as the lack of public value the lack of connection between tourists and students, the loss of the exhibition value of the courtyard, the cars overcrowding, the lack of functionality, and the lack of integration at the urban level. The project address both the need of interaction of students inside of UAUIM headquarter, and with the tourists around the building, in correlation with the entire very central area character of the city.

One of the main objective of this project was to include the development of green spaces, recreation areas, terraces, and social gathering places. To achieve this objective, several supporting actions are identified: creating an underground parking facility for the Intercontinental hotel, promoting the use of public transportation, establishing a new program for the regular maintenance of exhibitions and exhibits, revitalizing the interior courtyard. The project stetes that the STRUCTURAL CONSOLIDATION and SEISMIC SAFETY are PRIORITIES before any other interventions. Following the technical expertise, it is recommended that:

- a) The old building should receive a general foundation raft, and core drillings should be made down to this foundation, after which metal micropiles should be inserted and cement grout poured,
- b) The new building, which has a frame structure, should receive reinforced concrete diaphragms, and the upper structure should be detached from the foundation using seismic isolators for better seismic behavior,
- c) The urban planning building will have its frame structure consolidated and will receive reinforced concrete diaphragms and cores.

The project propose the vertical extension of the building on the south side with another level to accommodate model-making workshops. The classrooms on the 1st floor will be transformed into workshops to offer some acoustic comfort, while the new extension will house the former classrooms of the urban planning faculty.

Rearranging the attics to transform them into open coworking spaces for all students is also a proposal, valid only after a structural consolidation throughout the west zone, to be able to support the new equipment and the increased number of students.

The new cafeteria aims to improve communication with the university and students, offering more space for model-making workshops near existing facilities and potentially accommodating more people in a functionally designed space with optimized access.

results

Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier

Secțiune corp nou - Arhitectură

Secțiune corp vechi - Arhitectură

ENERGY EFFICIENCY

Thermal Insulation: Adequate thermal insulation in walls, roof, and floors to reduce heat loss.
Double or Triple Glazed Windows.

RENEWABLE ENERGY

Photovoltaic Solar Panels
Geothermal Energy Systems: Utilizing geothermal heat pumps for heating and cooling, which can significantly reduce energy consumption.
Wind Turbines integrated into the building's design, placed on the terrace.

AIR QUALITY

Heat Recovery Ventilation (HRV): Installing a mechanical ventilation system with heat recovery that improves indoor air quality and reduces heat loss.

SUSTAINABLE MATERIALS

Use of recycled materials - recycled plastic 3D printed for panels (the panels in the inner courtyard); recycled glass for forming colored glass panels (the panels on Academiei Street).

SMART SYSTEMS AND AUTOMATION

Building Management Systems (BMS): Implementing an intelligent building management system that monitors and controls energy consumption, lighting, and HVAC.

DYNAMIC RENEWAL
In a century characterized by accelerated climate change and heightened environmental awareness, the adoption of sustainable solutions has become more pervasive across all fields of society. The 'Ion Mincu' University of Architecture and Urbanism plays a pivotal role in shaping the future generations of architects and urban planners in Romania—professionals who must be equipped to respond to the evolving challenges of the built environment. The intervention strategy is grounded in economic feasibility and focuses on essential modernization actions, including structural consolidation, thermal retrofit, vertical extension, shading systems installation, and an efficient reorganization of internal spaces. The existing spatial configuration is largely maintained, with targeted modifications to enhance functionality. The basement is reconfigured for model-making studios, the cafeteria is relocated to the ground floor of the Urbanism building along Edgar Quinet Street, and administrative functions are moved to a new vertical upper floor. The attic is transformed into coworking and lounge spaces for students, while the sports hall is reconfigured to accommodate a large amphitheater through a retractable system, optimizing its use as a multi-use space.

TUTORING TEAM

- Prof. PhD arch. Anghel Star
- lect. PhD arch. Dana N. Armerosiu
- Asist. PhD student arch. Mihai Laurentiu Pirvan
- conf. PhD arch. Zina Vazari
- lect. PhD arch. Oana Arvanit
- conf. PhD arch. Mihaela Bernadescu
- lect. PhD arch. Andreea Vidrescu
- arch. I. Jean Calin Stescu
- lect. PhD arch. Oana M. Păscu
- asist. PhD arch. Ing. Cătălin Năzăroiu
- asist. PhD arch. Roxana Axiroie
- lect. PhD arch. Andreea Heljosean
- asist. PhD arch. Sorin Manca
- lect. PhD Ing. Alexandru Iordan
- lect. PhD Ing. Gabriel Dănilă

URBAN SCALE | stud. arch. Bots Ioana, stud. arch. Costea Mădălina Roxana, stud. arch. Popescu Ana

ACADEMIEI STREET FACADE SHADING SOLUTIONS

ARCHITECTURAL SCALE | stud. arch. Vircea David, stud. arch. Nedelcu Irina, stud. arch. Tudor Sapina

TECHNICAL DETAILING SCALE | stud. arch. Danc Larissa, stud. arch. Roman Cristiana, stud. arch. Tudor Filip Radu

University Urban Slab

Students

Alexandru Hergehelegiu
 Alexandru Nastasa
 Cristian Popa
 Vlad Badiu
 Adelina Burulea-Dragoș
 Carolina-Elena Zecheru
 Chirilă Mădălina Alexandra
 Clapan Maria-Elena
 Rusu Azaria-Bianca

The project is grounded in the systematic application of sustainability principles across all scales of intervention, encompassing urban, architectural, and detailed constructive levels. An integrated and sustainable approach is proposed, aiming primarily to enhance the building's energy efficiency, accessibility, and functionality, while respecting and preserving its historical and aesthetic character. The development strategy is structured around three fundamental pillars: urban integration, energy efficiency, and universal accessibility.

At the urban scale, the concept of the "university urban slab" is adopted, unifying the School of Architecture building and the Palace of the University of Bucharest into a coherent urban entity. This approach fosters the harmonious integration of the ensemble into the existing urban fabric, respecting the specific character of each adjacent area. By carefully addressing the urban context, the project contributes to the visual and functional coherence of the site, ensuring spatial continuity and enhancing its cultural and aesthetic potential.

At the architectural scale, the intervention focuses on improving energy performance and reactivating underutilized spaces. Measures such as the implementation of thermal insulation systems and ventilated façades are proposed to increase the building's energy efficiency and users' thermal comfort. For instance, a new ventilated façade is designed for the Faculty of Urbanism building, maintaining the proportions of the original modernist façade, while thermal insulation of structural elements in the newer wing minimizes heat loss. These interventions aim to reduce energy consumption for heating and cooling, without compromising the historical character of the building.

By integrating sustainability principles into all intervention levels, the project aims to foster the competencies necessary for designing and implementing architectural solutions that respect and protect the environment. The proposed interventions not only enhance energy performance and users' comfort but also preserve the integrity and aesthetic quality of the building.

results

Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier

results

Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier

SE PROPUNE FOTOSIREA MASURII CA SPAIU PUBLIC DE FURNICARE OCASIONALA PE TIMPUL VERII, ACCESUL PUBLICULUI FINE CONTROLAT PRIN INCHIDEREA SI CONTROLAREA ACCESELOR PE RECARE E AJ. INTRAREA PRINCIPALA FACANDU-SE PRIN CURTEA INTERIOARA

FROM A CIRCULATION POINT OF VIEW, ALL THE PROPOSED INTERVENTIONS TAKE INTO ACCOUNT ACCESSIBILITY AND CONNECTING SPACES, SO THAT FROM THE INNER COURTYARD YOU CAN REACH BOTH TERRACES, BUT ALSO THE INTERIOR SPACES THROUGH SEVERAL SERIES OF STEPS, RAMPS OR STAIRS

results

Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier

results
Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier

INSTALATII VENTILATIE CU RECUPERARE DE CALDURA EFICIENTA ENERGETICA IMPACT vizual

VERSIILE PANOURI FOTOVOLTAICE RANDBAND SI CALCULE

PV system section	PV modules	Power (kWp)
PV system section 1	150 PV modules	57.00 kWp
PV system section 2	57 PV modules	17.10 kWp
PV system section 3	58 PV modules	17.40 kWp
PV system section 4	58 PV modules	17.40 kWp

Monthly values
Energy yield

Profitability analysis

Inverter designs

DETALIU PLANTATIE CU REZERVARE PENTRU MENTINEREA APEI LA RADACINI

DETALIU PLANTATIE CU "FRENCH DRAIN"

DRAIN DE PAVIMENT "FRANDEZA PERI" CU UCHI INTREREA APELII DE BAZICEL

Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier results

The project is grounded in the systematic application of sustainability principles across a full scale of intervention, encompassing urban, architectural, and detailed constructive levels. An integrated and sustainable approach is proposed, aiming primarily to enhance the building's energy efficiency, accessibility, and functionality, while respecting and preserving its historical and aesthetic character. The development strategy is structured around three fundamental pillars: urban integration, energy efficiency, and universal accessibility. At the urban scale, the project adopts the concept of the "University Urban Slab" to unify the School of Architecture and the University of Bucharest buildings into a coherent urban entity that enhances spatial continuity and cultural value, while at the architectural scale, the intervention prioritizes energy performance and the reactivation of underused spaces through targeted measures, thus balancing sustainability with the preservation of the site's historical identity.

TUTORING TEAM

- Prof. PhD. arch. Argelios Stan
- lect. PhD. arch. Daniela N. Arsenova
- Asist. PhD. student arch. Mihai Laurențiu Păvăni
- conf. PhD. arch. Zina Mazri
- lect. PhD. arch. Gana Avram
- conf. PhD. arch. Mihaela-Irămărescu
- lect. PhD. arch. Adrian Vidrascu
- arch. Lucian Călugăreanu
- lect. PhD. arch. Gana Mihaela
- asst. PhD. arch. Iug. Cătălin Neagoe
- asst. PhD. arch. Roxana Axinche
- lect. PhD. arch. Andrei Proloboan
- asst. PhD. arch. Sorin Manea
- lect. PhD. ing. Alexandru I. Iatan
- lect. PhD. ing. Saonel Cătălina

URBAN SCALE | stud. arch. Ghita Madalina, stud. arch. Dorian Elena, stud. arch. Rusu Azalia

SITE PLAN PROPOSAL AXONOMETRIC VIEW

ARCHITECTURAL SCALE | stud. arch. Ferihelegia Alexandra, stud. arch. Neacsu Alexandru, stud. arch. Popa Cristian

TECHNICAL DETAILING SCALE | stud. arch. Radu Vlad, stud. arch. Burulesa-Dragos Adelina, stud. arch. Zedneru Carolina

Spatial Continuity through Sustainability

Students

Anastasia Avram
 Teodor Mihai Munteanu
 Bianca Iulia Zamfir
 Alexandru Cristian Gîsculescu-Angheliu
 Emanuel Cristian Lungu
 Mihai Marinescu
 Ege Bolat
 Diana-Elena Murariu
 Ana-Maria Pârvulescu

The project is guided by the concept of spatial continuity, ensuring that all interventions are harmoniously integrated to create a coherent and functional environment while minimizing environmental impact.

The intervention strategy is based on a rigorous evaluation of the building's current needs and untapped potential. Structural consolidation, thermal rehabilitation, and the introduction of dynamic shading systems on façades are proposed to address energy efficiency while maintaining the building's aesthetic qualities.

Interior reorganization focuses on improving ventilation, reducing cooking odors, and facilitating fluid circulation between key functional areas. For instance, the cafeteria is relocated to a brighter, better-ventilated ground floor space, while a new student hub is created in the attic, fostering collaboration, creativity, and community spirit among students and faculty members.

Circulation is optimized through directional markings—colored or textured pathways placed on floors and walls—to guide users toward key functions such as administration offices, the library, and lecture halls. In addition, the use of modern technologies is explored, such as mobile applications and strategically placed digital panels, to provide real-time information on facilities and services, thereby enhancing spatial navigation.

Dynamic façade shading solutions and the use of smart materials are introduced to maximize energy performance and improve the overall aesthetic of the building. Particular attention is given to ensuring a healthy indoor environment by utilizing advanced ventilation technologies aimed at optimizing air quality and thermal comfort.

accessibility

public functions

green spaces

TNB Park
200 m

Coltea Park
250 m

Cismigiu Park
650 m

Saint George Park
510 m

Step 1:

2

Step 2:

2

Step 3:

2

LAYOUT OF PEDESTRIAN AREA – EDGAR QUINET St.

results

Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier

results

Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier

results

Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier

Plan Etaj 1

results

Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier

Technical solutions

- high performance windows systems
- terrace insulation with use finishing
- insulation control elements / sun blinds
- photovoltaic panels
- heat pumps

SPATIAL COHERENCE

This building, a symbol of architectural education in Romania, is situated in a central area surrounded by structures of significant historical and cultural value. Constrained in a different era, the building no longer fully meets contemporary requirements regarding accessibility, sustainability, and functionality. The proposed interventions aim to address these needs through a modern approach while preserving the building's historical character. The intervention strategy is based on a rigorous evaluation of the building's current needs and untapped potential. Structural consolidation, thermal rehabilitation, and the introduction of dynamic shading systems or facades are proposed to address energy efficiency, while maintaining the building's aesthetic qualities. Interior reorganization focuses on improving ventilation, reducing cooking odors, and facilitating fluid circulation between key functional areas. For instance, the cafeteria is relocated to a brighter, better-ventilated ground floor space, while a new student hub is created in the attic, fostering collaboration, creativity, and community spirit among students and faculty members.

TUTORING TEAM

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- lect. PhD. arch. Andrei Vidrescu
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- lect. PhD. arch. Oana Mădăscu
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- lect. PhD. ing. Alexandru Iatan
- lect. PhD. ing. Gabriel Cășilă

URBAN SCALE | stud. arch. Bogdan Ștef. arch. Mariana Oana, stud. arch. Parvulescu Ana-Maria

ARCHITECTURAL SCALE | stud. arch. Zamfir Bianca Iulia, stud. arch. Avram Anastasia, stud. arch. Munteanu Ioscor

TECHNICAL DETAILING SCALE | stud. arch. Căstulescu Anghela Alexandru, Cristian, stud. arch. Lungu Emeline Cristalin, stud. arch. Măntescu Mihai

Implementation of the Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier

NEW BULGARIAN UNIVERSITY

Introduction

The primary objective of the INCEPT Climate Neutral Design Studio at NBU was to incorporate principles of sustainable and energy-efficient architectural design into the Architecture Program at NBU. The test studio focused on the concept of a “Climate Neutral District”, using a site near Mramor village as a key, easily replicable case study. The architectural design phase emphasized the Nearly Zero Energy Building (NZEB) concept within the framework of the Climate Neutral District model. The goal was to develop a conceptual model of sustainable housing at both the architectural and urban planning levels, serving as a foundation for creating a Climate Neutral District model.

Timeline

At the New Bulgarian University, Department of Architecture, the Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier took place in the autumn semester of the 2024/2025 academic year, from October 2024 to February 2025. The Atelier was conducted for 15 weeks, with sessions of four academic hours each week. Thirty fifth-year Architecture students participated in the atelier. They were divided into groups of 3 or 4 students.

Site characteristics

Several potential locations were evaluated for the project site selection. In addition to local microclimate details, various factors were considered, including existing urban development trends, provisions outlined in the Sofia Master Plan, transport accessibility, and economic aspects. Assessments of the Mramor site highlighted both natural and anthropogenic advantages. The chosen area is situated in the northwestern part of the Sofia Valley, on the old river terraces of the Blato River, within the Sofia Municipality region, offering convenient transport connections. Moreover, the site is designated as a low-rise residential district according to the Sofia Municipality Master Plan and benefits from favorable weather conditions and greenfield characteristics. For these reasons, it was deemed a suitable location for establishing a growing community aligned with sustainable development principles.

Mentors

Georgi Georgiev, PhD Arch., Professor
 Zdravko Georgiev, PhD, Lecturer
 Peter Petrov, PhD Arch., Senior Assistant Professor
 Eleonora Gaydarova, PhD, Lecturer
 Petko Georgiev, PhD Cand. Arch., Lecturer

Guest Lecturers

Nadia Nikolova-Deme, PhD, SOFENA Energy Efficiency Agency
 Alexander Stankov, PhD, Center for Energy Efficiency EnEffect

Mramor Lake Park Residential Complex

Students

Svetlana Dimitrova
Ivan Mikov
Mario Legurski

Multi-family residences

The isolation and peace of mind in the property, the low-rise and the low-density of building are the most essential characteristics of the environment with which the project works. Hidden in the greenery and at the same time easily accessible, the multi-family residential buildings (14 in total) are skillfully “woven” into their surroundings. Clear of unnecessary details and bold in terms of accents, they are a place to live that does not lack space, luxury and amenities. The buildings are accessible from the surrounding boulevards and from the inner-neighborhood streets. They are built in groups with a large distance between them, with the space being separated like a garden. The large distance increases the quality of living. The configuration of the buildings defines two public spaces - street/s and courtyard – which separate the residents and give them the opportunity and space for socialization and relaxation. The courtyard becomes a protected place FOR children to play, and the streets act as an informal meeting place. The residential units are large and spacious, carefully configured in elongated corridor structures, designed on two levels. Parking and parking of the residents’ vehicles is organized in a garage on the underground floor. The ground floor of some of the buildings is freed up for commercial services, sports clubs, office spaces, etc. The availability of commercial services on the ground floor increases the profitability and makes the investment more convincing, and access to the residential part is designed with a central communication core. Each building houses 2 (4) apartments - one (two) three-room and one (two) four-room, distributed evenly on the ground and first floors. Privacy (lack of visual contact between the residents) is achieved by alternating terraces with closed parts along the periphery of the buildings.

Single-family residences

The project includes 33 equal detached single-family residential buildings – rotated and broken, with a characteristic residential scale. The buildings are on two floors. Each building has a separate entrance (directly from the ground level), a small yard, a terrace and two parking spaces. The apartments have convenient configurations in terms of planning - they have all the functional areas necessary for modern living by families of different composition. On the first level (with an area of about 100 m²) the rooms of the functional group “day” are distributed. On the second level (with an area of about 85 m²) three bedrooms with adjacent sanitary facilities are planned. In terms of volume, the buildings represent a well balanced composition of grouped, square-planned residential VOLUMES, clad in wood and harmoniously integrated into the environment. The distance between them is 10 - 12 - 14 m, which is sufficient and provides opportunities for creating intimacy. There are no problems with sunlight - shading is either non-existent or minimized and within the limits of what is favorable. In this regard, the project achieves good comfort and high hygiene indicators. Single-family residential buildings with SMALL PRIVATE YARDS give a fresh and characteristic look to the neighborhood. They create numerous places for relaxation and privacy, as well as opportunities for further development by their residents to give individuality. The project offers a solution that combines the advantages of individual living with collective living - living becomes shared. The spaces are both private and public and form both an individual and a holistic appearance of the environment.

MRAMOR residential complex
LAKE PARK

	SINGLE FAMILY HOUSE		PLAYGROUND		ROAD		AMPHITHEATER
	SPORTS CENTER		POND		CAR		TENNIS COURT
	MULTI-FAMILY RES. BUILDING		TOTEM		PRIVATE GARDEN		BASKETBALL COURT
	SERVICE BUILDING		HILL		HEDGE		PARKING POCKET

New Bulgarian University

ARCM902 Training: Facility management and energy efficiency

Svetlana Dimitrova
Ivan Mikov
Mario Legurski

GROUND FLOOR
1:200

GROUND FLOOR
1:200

SECOND FLOOR
1:200

SECOND FLOOR
1:200

ROOF
1:200

UNDER-
GROUND
FLOOR
1:200

ELEVATION
1:200

ELEVATION
1:200

ELEVATION
1:200

SECTION
1:200

ELEVATION
1:200

ELEVATION
1:200

SECTION
1:200

FRESH AIR SYSTEM ventilation without heat loss

The basic principle of heat recovery is the same as in any other ventilation system: fresh air is supplied to the "dry" living spaces such as the living room, bedroom and office. In addition, humid air is discharged through the "wet" areas such as the kitchen, bathroom and toilet. In a heat recovery system, the supply of fresh air and the exhaust air are completely mechanical via two fans in the ventilation module. They are kept in balance with each other. In this way, the flow rate is automatically and constantly adjusted depending on the area of the different rooms and the desired comfortable temperature and energy efficiency. That is why this system is also called balanced ventilation (and ventilation system with heat recovery).

TREATMENT PLANT purification of domestic wastewater

The purification process takes place in three stages. Initially, raw wastewater enters a primary clarifier, where separation and decomposition of organic substances take place. In the primary tank for primary treatment or denitrification, all fats, oils, undissolved substances and other coarse, heavy particles that are undissolved or insoluble fall. Oils and fats are separated on the surface, forming a layer floating in the water. Solid, undissolved and insoluble substances, heavy elements fall to the bottom, where they form the so-called wastewater sludge. Then the wastewater passes through an outlet filter before entering the reactor, where a process of aerobic decomposition and filtration takes place.

The reactor is filled with a specially developed biological mass that is aerated on a natural physiological principle with natural draft or chimney effect. This enzyme helps the growth of bacteria by providing them with a favorable environment for their reproduction.

HEAT PUMP efficient heating and hot water

A heat pump uses technology similar to that found in a refrigerator or air conditioner. It extracts heat from a source such as the surrounding air, geothermal energy stored in the ground, or nearby water sources or waste heat from a factory. It then amplifies and transfers the heat to where it is needed. Because most of the heat is transferred rather than generated, heat pumps are much more efficient than conventional heating technologies such as boilers or electric heaters and can be cheaper to run. The energy output in the form of heat is usually several times greater than the energy required to power the heat pump, usually in the form of electricity. For example, the coefficient of performance for a typical household heat pump is around three, meaning the energy output is three times greater than the electrical energy used to operate it. This makes current models 3-5 times more energy efficient than gas boilers. Heat pumps can be combined with other heating systems, usually gas, in hybrid configurations.

ENERGY EFFICIENT GLASS COMPOSITION light without heat loss

Triple glazing is a two-chamber system with two air or gas chambers between the panes. They provide an additional layer of insulation, which significantly reduces heat loss. This is especially effective in cold climates. The three layers of glass and the insulation chambers offer excellent protection against external noise. The likelihood of condensation on the inner panes is even lower than with double glazing. Triple glazing is a recommended choice for areas with extreme climate conditions, where maximum energy efficiency and thermal insulation are essential. They are suitable for both residential and commercial buildings, especially in cold regions or where a high degree of noise insulation is required.

GOOD THERMAL INSULATION constant microclimate

The building facade is usually the largest surface that separates the interior of the building from the external environment. Accordingly, it is also the place where a large amount of heat loss can occur. Thermal insulation of the facade (external walls) from the outside is an effective way to protect against heat loss. Stone wool systems work to insulate the vertical envelope of any building - whether it is a single house or an entire apartment block. They are able to prevent damage caused by weather-related temperature loads and condensation problems. The main advantages of a plastered facade with stone wool include preventing heat loss by reducing thermal bridges in the outer shell of buildings - with proper external thermal insulation, stone wool can fill all unwanted cavities and improve the energy efficiency of an entire building.

CONSUMPTION OF ELECTRICITY

without hot water and heating

type of building	kWh / month
HOUSE single family residence	
per unit	700
for the whole complex	23 100
APARTEMENT in a multi-family building	
per unit	600
for the whole complex	16 800
PUBLIC SPACES in a multi-family building	
per unit	300
for the whole complex	12 600
SPORTS BUILDING	1000
SERVICE BUILDING	1500
PARK, STREET LIGHTS...	1000
TOTAL consumption	56 000

CONSUMPTION OF ELECTRICITY

for hot water and heating, during winter

type of building	kWh/month
Average consumption 1 sq.m. for HOUSES	6.61
Total consumption for all HOUSES	30 811.16
Average consumption 1 sq.m. for APARTMENTS	5.63
Total consumption for all APARTMENTS	52 641.61
SERVICE BUILDING	1 763.92
SPORTS BUILDING	1 305.95
TOTAL for the whole complex	86 522.64

AVERAGE MONTHLY CONSUMPTION for the whole complex	105 511.32 kWh/month
AVERAGE MONTHLY COLLECTION for the whole complex	74 405.89 kWh/month
CONCLUSION	- 31 105.43 kWh/month
IRR * internal norm for return	11.52%
REDEMPTION PERIOD - years	7.59

GENERATION OF ELECTRICITY

вид	kWh / месец
Biaxial photovoltaics from a photovoltaic park 739.20 m2 collection area 155.23 kWp power	22 573.49
Photovoltaics mounted on the roofs of buildings 2 719.20 m2 collection area 571.03 kWp power	51 835.40
TOTAL generation of electricity	74 405.89

PHOTOVOLTAICS

The photovoltaic arrays used in the complex are composed of 16 pcs. /4 rows of 4 columns/ photovoltaic panels with a size of 1650x1000 mm, each of them consisting of 60 pcs. photovoltaic cells.

The photovoltaic installed at the treatment plant are on a movable arm, which directs them along two axes - an angle relative to the direction of the world and an angle relative to the earth's surface.

The solar panels mounted on the buildings are placed in a horizontal position.

#2402 Training Facility management and energy efficiency

Svetlana Dimitrova
Ivan Mikov
Mario Legurski

MRAMOR

residential complex

LAKE PARK

SINGLE FAMILY HOUSE

The project includes 33 EQUAL DETACHED SINGLE-FAMILY RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS - rotated and broken, with a characteristic residential scale. The buildings are on two floors.

Each building has a separate entrance (directly from the ground level), a small yard, a terrace and two parking spaces. Houses have convenient configurations in terms of planning - they have all the functional areas necessary for modern living by families of different composition. On the first level (with an area of about 100 m²) the rooms of the functional group "day" are distributed. On the second level (with an area of about 85 m²) three bedrooms with adjacent sanitary facilities are planned.

In terms of volume, the buildings represent a WELL BALANCED COMPOSITION OF GROUPED, SQUARE-PLANNED RESIDENTIAL VOLUMES, clad in wood and harmoniously integrated into the environment. The distance between them is 10 - 12 - 14 m, which is sufficient and provides opportunities for creating intimacy. There are no problems with sunlight - shading is either non-existent or minimized and within the limits of what is tolerable. In this regard, the project achieves good comfort and high hygiene indicators.

Single-family residential buildings with SMALL PRIVATE YARDS give a fresh and characteristic look to the neighborhood. They create numerous places for relaxation and privacy, as well as opportunities for further development by their residents to give individually. The project offers a solution that combines the advantages of individual living with collective living - LIVING BECOMES SHARED. The spaces are both private and public and form both an individual and a holistic appearance of the environment.

MULTI-FAMILY RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS

THE ISOLATION AND PEACE OF MIND IN THE PROPERTY, THE LOW-RISE AND THE LOW-DENSITY OF BUILDING ARE THE MOST ESSENTIAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE ENVIRONMENT WITH WHICH THE PROJECT WORKS. Hidden in the greenery and at the same time easily accessible, the multi-family residential buildings (24 in total) are subtly "woven" into their surroundings. Clear of unnecessary details and bold in terms of accents, they are a place to live that does not lack space, luxury and amenities.

The buildings are accessible from the surrounding boulevards. THEY ARE BUILT IN GROUPS WITH A LARGE DISTANCE BETWEEN THEM, with the space being separated like a garden. The large distance increases the quality of living. The configuration of the buildings defines two public spaces - streets and courtyard - which separate the residents and give them the opportunity and space for socialization and relaxation. THE COURTYARD BECOMES A PROTECTED PLACE FOR CHILDREN TO PLAY, AND THE STREETS ACT AS AN INFORMAL MEETING PLACE.

The residential units are large and spacious, carefully configured in elongated corridor structures, designed on two levels. Parking and parking of the residents' vehicles is organized in a garage on the underground floor. The ground floor of some of the buildings is freed up for commercial services, sports clubs, office spaces, etc. (THE AVAILABILITY OF COMMERCIAL SERVICES ON THE GROUND FLOOR INCREASES THE PROFITABILITY AND MAKES THE INVESTMENT MORE CONVINING), and access to the residential part is designed with a central communication core. Each building houses 2 (4) apartments - one (two) three-room and one (two) four-room, distributed evenly on the ground and first floors. Privacy (lack of visual contact between the residents) is achieved by alternating terraces with closed parts along the periphery of the buildings.

CONSUMPTION OF ELECTRICITY

without hot water and heating		
type of building	per unit	kWh / month
HOUSE	per unit	700
single family residence	for the whole complex	23 100
APARTMENT	per unit	600
in a multi-family building	for the whole complex	16 800
PUBLIC SPACES	per unit	200
in a multi-family building	for the whole complex	12 400
SPORTS BUILDING	per unit	1000
SERVICE BUILDING	per unit	1000
PARK, STREET LIGHTS,...	per unit	1000
TOTAL consumption		56 000

for hot water and heating, during winter		
type of building	per unit	kWh / month
Average consumption 1 sq.m. for HOUSES		6.61
Total consumption for all HOUSES		30 811.16
Average consumption 1 sq.m. for APARTMENTS		5.63
Total consumption for all APARTMENTS		52 641.61
SERVICE BUILDING		1763.92
SPORTS BUILDING		1 395.95
TOTAL for the whole complex		96 522.64

AVERAGE MONTHLY CONSUMPTION for the whole complex 102 812.24 kWh/month

AVERAGE MONTHLY PRODUCTION for the whole complex 74 463.89 kWh/month

AVERAGE MONTHLY SHORTAGE 31 888.00 kWh/month

cost and savings	
	EUR
Investment in photovoltaics	1 452 528
Investment in heatpumps	2 438 534.80
TOTAL investment	3 891 116.80
Average yearly savings from photovoltaics	272 574.55
Average yearly savings from using heatpumps	240 343.76
AVERAGE YEARLY SAVINGS	512 918.31

CONCLUSION

IRR 11.52%

PAYBACK PERIOD - years 7.59

PHOTOVOLTAIC PARK

production of electricity

type of panels	kWh / month
Bifacial photovoltaics from a photovoltaic park	22 573.49
179.20 m ² collection area	155.23 kWp power
Photovoltaics mounted on the roofs of buildings	51 835.40
2 719.20 m ² collection area	571.63 kWp power
TOTAL production	74 408.89

photovoltaic panels

The photovoltaic arrays used in the complex are composed of 16 pcs. /A rows of 4 columns/ photovoltaic panels with a size of 1650x1000 mm, each of them consisting of 40 pcs. photovoltaic cells.

The photovoltaic installed at the treatment plant are on a movable arm, which directs them along two axes - an angle relative to the direction of the world and an angle relative to the earth's surface.

The solar panels mounted on the buildings are placed in a horizontal position.

*Calculations are based on the use of a heat pump and are only valid for the months during the heating season.

*Calculations are for average monthly production, via <https://4.01.ec.europa.eu/energy/index.html> (incl. loss of electricity of 25%, due to atmospheric fluctuations and losses from the storage of electricity energy in batteries).

*Calculations are for average monthly production, via <https://4.01.ec.europa.eu/energy/index.html> (incl. loss of electricity of 25%, due to atmospheric fluctuations and losses from the storage of electricity energy in batteries).

*Calculations are based on an electricity price of 0.21 BGN/kWh and a coefficient of efficiency of the thermoelectric panels of 3.2 (Bosch).

Mramor Mixed type Residential Complex

Students

Viktoria Georgieva
Nikol Diakova
Zlatka Kardaleva

The project is located on road “Dobroslavsko Shose”, outside the village of Mramor. Currently, the land is agricultural and borders other agricultural areas, which could also change their intended use in the future if there is a need for growth. The project offers a variety of functions and includes residential buildings, an office building with an abundance of public spaces — a restaurant, pharmacy, shop, telecommunications office, multimedia hall (available for rent), café, post office, and four office spaces on the second floor, as well as a park area with a children’s playground and a communal barbecue. A concept developed aimed at attracting people from various social groups. Two types of single-family houses are offered, placed either on individual plots or grouped into clusters of two or three. Additionally, there are four residential buildings consisting of four floors with underground parking, suitable for young families or elderly people due to the smaller size of the apartments. The entrance to the complex is from road “Dobroslavsko Shose”. The complex is divided into a south and north parts, split by a main road. Additionally, there is a secondary main road that intersects the first one. The park zone and the office building — accessible directly from the main street — are situated at the very heart of the complex and the multi-family residential buildings are to the south of it.

The single-family houses and villas are situated on the periphery to create a more pleasant and secluded living space. Each house is equipped with a photovoltaic system that produces enough energy to meet all household needs. The PV panels are positioned on the roofs to ensure sufficient sunlight exposure. The houses also feature solar management with artificial intelligence for residents’ convenience and maximum energy efficiency. The community building has a green roof, and the photovoltaic panels are integrated into the facade. Additionally, a system of air-source heat pumps is planned, which, due to their efficiency, are suitable for passive and low-energy houses. In the park, micro-wind turbines are intended to be installed, consisting of double blades with a vertical axis in the shape of a leaf and a synchronous micro-generator with permanent magnets. Each turbine generates enough energy to power a household of four residents.

The complex features 12 luxurious villas, each 165 sq.m. of living space, with a garage for two cars, placed on separate plots. The villas are insulated with 16 cm stone wool and meet the zero-energy standards. Twelve solar panels are installed on each garage.

The project also includes 73 single-family houses, each with 142 sq.m. of living area, outdoor parking for two cars, and positioned on separate plots with access paths. These houses are insulated with 14 cm of stone wool. On the roof of the second floor, there are 11 solar panels, making the house independent energy-wise.

The residential buildings are centrally located within the property and are well-served by the complex's roundabout road. They feature underground parking with separate entry and exit points. Apartments face south, southeast, or southwest. The complex offers a variety of 2, 3, or 4-room apartments, catering to different family sizes — from single individuals to larger households. The upper floors are set back from the south side to allow for beautiful, spacious southern terraces, more natural light, and heat inside the residences. About 25 solar panels with southern orientation can be installed on each roof.

Office building with an abundance of public spaces — a restaurant, pharmacy, shop, telecommunications office, multimedia hall (available for rent), café, post office, and four office spaces on the second floor

Cost-Benefit Analysis for the Use of RES (Renewable Energy Sources)

Type of building	Area (sq.m)	Approx. Power (kWp)	Investment (EUR)	Payback Period
Single-family house	142	Approx. 3.2 kWp	6,400	6.4 years
Multi-family building	700	Approx. 10 kWp	20,000	6.5 years
Villa	164	Approx. 5 kWp	10,000	8 years
Public building	3,460	116–162 kWp	260,000	5.8 years

Photovoltaic Systems

- Solar roof tiles
- Function both as roofing and a solar system, maintaining the building's aesthetics.
- Facade-Integrated Solar Panels-BIPV (Building integrated photovoltaics)
- Integrated directly into the building's structural elements.
- Solar Windows
- AI-Based Solar Management
- Solar systems managed and optimized using artificial intelligence.

Air-to-Water Heat Pumps

- Up to **90%** of the heat from used indoor air can be effectively utilized.
- Suitable for **passive or low-energy** houses.

Energy Storage System ESS

- Optimizing energy generation
- Reducing grid dependency
- Key applications:
 - self-consumption
 - balancing the intermittent nature of renewable energy
 - storage and distribution utilities

Micro Wind Turbines

- A micro wind turbine composed of:
 - A **double-blade vertical axis** shaped like a leaf.
 - A **synchronous microgenerator** with permanent magnets.
- Generates **enough energy to power a household with 4 residents.**

results

Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier

The project is located on road "Dobroslavsko Shose", outside the village of Mramor. Currently, the land is agricultural and borders other agricultural areas, which could also change their intended use in the future if there is a need for growth. Our project offers a variety of functions and includes residential buildings, an office building with an abundance of public spaces — a restaurant, pharmacy, shop, telecommunications office, multimedia hall (available for rent), café, post office, and four office spaces on the second floor, as well as a park area with a children's playground and a communal barbecue. We have developed a concept aimed at attracting people from various social groups. We offer two types of single-family houses, placed either on individual plots or grouped into clusters of two or three. Additionally, there are four residential buildings consisting of four floors with underground parking, suitable for young families or elderly people due to the smaller size of the apartments.

The entrance to the complex is from road "Dobroslavsko Shose". The complex is divided into a south and north parts, split by a main road. Additionally, there is a secondary main road that intersects the first one. The park zone and the office building — accessible directly from the main street — are situated at the very heart of the complex and the multi-family residential buildings are to the south of it. The single-family houses and villas are situated on the periphery to create a more pleasant and secluded living space. Each house is equipped with a photovoltaic system that produces enough energy to meet all household needs. The PV panels are positioned on the roofs to ensure sufficient sunlight exposure. The houses also feature solar management with artificial intelligence for resident convenience and maximum energy efficiency.

The community building has a green roof, and the photovoltaic panels are integrated into the facade. Additionally, a system of air-source heat pumps is planned, which, due to their efficiency, are suitable for passive and low-energy houses.

In the park, micro-wind turbines are intended to be installed, consisting of double blades with a vertical axis in the shape of a leaf and a synchronous micro-generator with permanent magnets. Each turbine generates enough energy to power a household of four residents.

SITE PLAN
M 1:2000

The complex features 12 luxurious villas, each 165 sq.m. of living space, with a garage for two cars, placed on separate plots. The villas are insulated with 16 cm stone wool and meet the zero-energy standards. Twelve solar panels are installed on each garage.

The project also includes 73 single-family houses, each with 142 sq.m. of living area, outdoor parking for two cars, and positioned on separate plots with access paths. These houses are insulated with 14 cm of stone wool. On the roof of the second floor, there are 11 solar panels, making the house independent energy-wise.

The residential buildings are centrally located within the property and are well-served by the complex's roundabout road. They feature underground parking with separate entry and exit points. Apartments face south, southeast, or southwest. The complex offers a variety of 2, 3, or 4-room apartments, catering to different family sizes — from single individuals to larger households. The upper floors are set back from the south side to allow for beautiful, spacious southern terraces, more natural light, and heat inside the residences. About 25 solar panels with southern orientation can be installed on each roof.

Office building with an abundance of public spaces — a restaurant, pharmacy, shop, telecommunications office, multimedia hall (available for rent), café, post office, and four office spaces on the second floor

Cost-Benefit Analysis for the Use of RES (Renewable Energy Sources)

Type of building	Area (sq.m)	Approx. Power (kWp)	Investment (EUR)	Payback Period
Single-family house	142	Approx. 3.2 kWp	6,400	6.4 years
Multi-family building	700	Approx. 10 kWp	20,000	6.5 years
Villa	164	Approx. 5 kWp	10,000	8 years
Public building	3,460	116–162 kWp	260,000	5.8 years

Photovoltaic Systems

- Solar roof tiles
- Function both as roofing and a solar system, maintaining the building's aesthetics.
- Facade-Integrated Solar Panels-BIPV (Building integrated photovoltaics)
- Integrated directly into the building's structural elements.
- Solar Windows
- AI-Based Solar Management
- Solar systems managed and optimized using artificial intelligence.

Air-to-Water Heat Pumps

- Up to 90% of the heat from used indoor air can be effectively utilized.
- Suitable for **passive or low-energy houses**.

Energy Storage System ESS

- Optimizing energy generation
- Reducing grid dependency
- Key applications:
 - self-consumption
 - balancing the intermittent nature of renewable energy
 - storage and distribution utilities

Micro Wind Turbines

- A micro wind turbine composed of:
 - A **double-blade vertical axis** shaped like a leaf.
 - A **synchronous microgenerator** with permanent magnets.
 - Generates enough energy to power a household with 4 residents.

Residential Eco-Community in Mramor

Students

Izabel Rabadzhiyska
Yanka Ilieva
Slavina Georgieva

Masterplan Vision

Inspired by the site's natural topography, the masterplan weaves soft mobility routes pedestrian, cycling, and vehicular-across a forested landscape. Dense greenery functions as a buffer and climate moderator, shaping a healthy and livable environment.

Architecture

Each house features:

- private garden and garage
- open-plan living area
- three bedrooms and two bathrooms
- east-west orientation for passive ventilation

South-facing facades are equipped with sliding wooden louvres for summer shading. Every plot includes curated vegetation to enhance microclimate and privacy.

Construction & Materials

Modular steel structures ensure fast construction with low environmental impact. The insulation is made of natural sheep's wool, which is fire-resistant and regulates humidity, maintaining acoustic comfort and air quality. The materials are recyclable and, where possible, sourced locally.

Energy concept

Each unit integrates a heat pump system combined with solar panels, which provides heating, cooling, and hot water throughout the year. This completely self-sufficient system guarantees zero emissions, low operating costs, and long-term energy independence.

1.CHILDREN's CENTER

2.RETAIL CENTER

3.TYPICAL HOUSE

Consumption of electricity	
without hot water and heating	
Type of building	kWh / month
House	350
The whole residential complex	16 800
Retail Center	24 150
Park, Streer lights	3000
Total consumption:	43 950

for hot water and heating, during winter	
Type of building	kWh / month
Avarage consumption 1 sq.m. for HOUSES	5.8
Total consumption for all HOUSES	55 680
Retail Center	11 206
Total consumption:	66 890

Avarage Montly CONSUPMTION for the whole copmlex	165465 kWh
Avarage Montly PRODUCTION for the whole copmlex	84 206 kWh/m
cost and savings	
	lev
Investment inphotovoltaics	2 705 625
Investment hetapumps	1 518 426
Total investment:	4 224 051
	lev
Avarage yearly savings from inphotovoltaics	999 000
Avarage yearly savings from hetapumps	119 314
Avarage yearly savings:	1 118 314
Conclusion	
IRR	4.5%
Payback period - years	16.7

production of electricity	
type of panels	kWh / month
Monocrystalline panels, N-Type, Half-Cell Collection area - 750.8 m ² Power - 165.12 kWp	14 860.8
Monocrystalline panels, N-Type, Half-Cell Collection area - 3574.2 m ² Power - 770.5 kWp	69 345
Total production:	84 206

Residential Eco-Community in Mramor

Total area	93440m ²
Number of storeys	1 storey
Building types	Single-family
Parking spaces:	
Public	72
Private	96
Landscaping	80%

Key Advantages:

- ▶ Park-like environment
- ▶ Pedestrian- and bicycle-friendly environment
- ▶ Optimal building orientation and passive ventilation
- ▶ Designated yard areas
- ▶ Sports and recreation area
- ▶ Retail center and children's center
- ▶ Locally sourced materials – wood and stone

Site & Context

Located at the northern edge of Mramor village, the project spans 93,000 m² in a quiet, green zone just 2 km from Sofia Ring Road. The area combines natural beauty, clean air, and favorable climate—ideal for a low-density, sustainable neighborhood.

Masterplan Vision

Inspired by the site's natural topography, the masterplan weaves soft mobility routes—pedestrian, cycling, and vehicular—across a forested landscape. Dense greenery functions as a buffer and climate moderator, shaping a healthy and livable environment.

Architecture

- Each house features:
- Private garden and garage
- Open-plan living area
- Three bedrooms and two bathrooms
- East-west orientation for passive ventilation
- South-facing facades are equipped with sliding wooden louvers for summer shading. Every plot includes curated vegetation to enhance microclimate and privacy.

Construction & Materials

Modular steel structures ensure fast, low-impact construction. Insulation is provided by sheep wool—natural, fire-resistant, and moisture-regulating—supporting acoustic comfort and air quality. Materials are recyclable and locally sourced where possible.

Energy Concept

Each unit integrates a heat pump system combined with solar panels, providing year-round heating, cooling, and hot water. This fully self-sufficient system ensures zero emissions, low operating costs, and long-term energy independence.

Consumption of electricity	
without hot water and heating	
Type of building	kWh / month
House	350
The whole residential complex	16 800
Retail Center	24 150
Park, Street lights	3000
Total consumption:	43 950

for hot water and heating, during winter	
Type of building	kWh / month
Average consumption 1 sq.m. for HOUSES	5,8
Total consumption for all HOUSES	55 680
Retail Center	11 206
Total consumption:	66 890

Average Monthly CONSUMPTION for the whole complex		165465 kWh
cost and savings		
Investment in photovoltaics	2 705 625	lev
Investment in heat pumps	1 518 426	lev
Total investment:	4 224 051	lev
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Promotion and Dissemination of the Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier

Final International Event of the Incept Project

Sofia, 17 June 2025

Bogdan Bogdanov Library Building, Auditorium 2
New Bulgarian University

The Final International Event of the INCEPT Project (Erasmus+ KA220-HED – Cooperation Partnerships in Higher Education) was held on 17 June 2025 at the New Bulgarian University (NBU) in Sofia. The event marked the conclusion of the three-year collaboration among partner institutions, celebrating the project's achievements in sustainable architecture education and the integration of climate-neutral design principles into academic practice.

Participants included:

- Senior representatives from NBU,
- Project team members from:
 - New Bulgarian University (NBU),
 - "Ion Mincu" University of Architecture and Urbanism (UAUIM),
 - University of Zagreb, Faculty of Architecture (UNIZG),
- Architecture students from NBU, UAUIM, and UNIZG,
- Students from other study programs at NBU,
- Academic staff from NBU's Department of Architecture and other departments,
- Professionals and experts from the wider architectural community.

The Final International Event of the INCEPT Project was organized at the "Bogdan Bogdanov Library" building at New Bulgarian University. The day opened formally with an introduction by Professor Dr. Arch. Georgi Georgiev, INCEPT Project Lead at NBU, who reflected on the goals and achievements of the project. His address was followed by warm words of welcome from representatives of the university leadership, including:

- Emilia Dimitrova, PhD, Associate Professor, Vice-Rector for Research and Creative Activity,
 - Marieta Cvetkova, PhD, Director International Projects,
 - Vesela Popova, PhD Arch., Senior Assistant Professor, Head of the Department of Architecture,
- who all acknowledged the project's impact on architectural education and international collaboration.

Final International Event of the Incept Project: Sofia, 17 June 2025

Final International Event of the Incept Project

Sofia, 17 June 2025

Bogdan Bogdanov Library Building, Auditorium 2
New Bulgarian University

The final event included presentations from each of the three partner institutions. Professor Dr. Arch. Angelica Stan from "Ion Mincu" University of Architecture and Urbanism (UAUIM) presented the contributions of her team and institution to the INCEPT Project, followed by Sen. Lecturer Arch. Stanka Ostojić from the University of Zagreb, Faculty of Architecture, who shared insights into the Zagreb team's involvement and experiences. Professor Georgiev then returned to present NBU's perspective, focusing on the integration of climate-neutral strategies into the curriculum and student work.

Final International Event of the Incept Project: Sofia, 17 June 2025

Final International Event of the Incept Project

Sofia, 17 June 2025

Bogdan Bogdanov Library Building, Auditorium 2
New Bulgarian University

A particularly memorable part of the event was the awarding of certificates to students who had participated in the Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier, one of the project's core educational components. This moment acknowledged the dedication and creativity students demonstrated in developing forward-thinking, sustainable architectural solutions.

The recognition ceremony was followed by a guided tour of the atelier exhibition, where students from all three universities presented their projects in an informal setting. These short presentations encouraged lively discussion and exchange of ideas among students, faculty, and professionals alike, showcasing the practical outcomes of the collaborative design process.

Final International Event of the Incept Project: Sofia, 17 June 2025

Promotion and Dissemination of the Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier

Atelier certificate of completion

Each Atelier student was able to receive a certificate as an attest of the acquired knowledge. The participating universities were invited to use the certificate template to ensure mutual compliance and clarity.

Conclusion

The creation and implementation of the Intellectual Output 3 Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier within the INCEPT Project stands as a pivotal step in redefining architectural education to meet the urgent challenges of climate change and sustainability. By introducing integrated building design methodology supported by digital tools such as Building Information Modelling (BIM), the Atelier not only enhances students' technical competencies but also fosters their understanding of the entire building life cycle. This approach empowers future architects to address both operational and embodied carbon while adopting innovative solutions that reduce energy demand, minimize waste, and promote circular use of resources. In doing so, the Atelier directly contributes to the green transition and prepares students to design in alignment with the European Green Deal and climate neutrality objectives. Equally important, the Atelier cultivates green skills and digital literacy as essential components of contemporary architectural practice. Students are encouraged to explore passive strategies, low-energy concepts, and inclusive design solutions while developing a systemic awareness of how buildings interact with their broader urban and ecological contexts.

By engaging with real-world design challenges, such as urban regeneration and resource efficiency, participants learn to balance sustainability goals with creativity, aesthetics, and cultural values. This ensures that architectural education does not reduce sustainability to a technical requirement but rather embeds it as a core design principle at every stage of the process. The collaborative involvement of the partner universities — the New Bulgarian University, Ion Mincu University of Architecture and Urbanism, and the University of Zagreb — further strengthens the relevance and adaptability of IO3.

Altogether, 175 students, 18 mentors and 8 guest lecturers were included in Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier implementation, at all three partner universities. During one semester of the Master of Architecture programmes of partner universities, students were guided by teachers from various departments (architecture, urban planning, and building technology).

External guest lecturers included municipal office representatives, practicing architects, urban planners, conservationists, heritage experts, brownfield redesign experts, and other faculty members from various departments. This allowed transdisciplinarity of the Atelier, noticed through: the integration of diverse disciplines (architecture, urban planning, landscape design, building engineering, environmental science and social and cultural disciplines), focus on climate neutrality and implementation of sustainable design principles (energy efficiency, the use of renewable energy sources, and minimal environmental impact), technological innovation (smart building systems, eco-materials, innovative construction techniques) and lifecycle assessment, as well as collaborative learning ecosystem (hands-on approach, commitment based on own experience, theory and practice expert Guidance and innovative problem solving).

Through shared expertise, continuous evaluation, and refinement based on practical implementation, the results of the Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier represent a robust and transferable model of sustainable education in architecture. Ultimately, IO3 supports the specific objective of training students to design energy-efficient, low-carbon, and socially inclusive buildings, while equipping them with the vision and tools to lead the profession into a climate-resilient future. In this way, the Atelier not only fulfills the goals of the INCEPT Project but also contributes to shaping a generation of architects capable of driving Europe's transformation toward a sustainable and climate-neutral built environment.

A central approach to maintaining the ongoing relevance of the Climate Neutral Building Design Atelier is its implementation across additional university departments. This entails periodic revisions to integrate the most recent research findings in sustainable design, urban and landscape planning, and climate adaptation. Moreover, a continuous feedback mechanism from students and teachers is essential for adapting to shifting educational demands. By regularly refreshing the curriculum and instructional methods, the Atelier remains a crucial resource, enhancing institutional expertise and fostering long-term educational sustainability.

